

Graphics Lightbox Revisited: Constructing Graphics Light Box/Table for Studio Performance

By

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Abstract

*This study is an art-based action research which combined standard qualitative research methodology with the art based technique of production/creation of the light box. To Answer RQ1 (Research Question one) questionnaires were used to obtain data for the inquiry, sought directly from Students and Lecturers in tertiary institutions from Applied Art Departments. While production method detailing step by step processes were used to answer RQ2. The method used in the 3D production include: measuring, cutting and assemblage of the wood, and glass with necessary tools/equipment to achieve the desired output. A 6 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection from 100 respondents from 5 schools. It was analyzed using mean, frequency and standard deviation. The instrument used was titled: **Graphics Light box Revisited questionnaire (GLBRQ)**. The findings revealed that only few art departments in other schools visited possess a functional light box/light table for studio performance. This suggests the need for holistic studio equipment upgrade nationwide. It was recommended that there should be an increased practical research to produce additional needed equipment for fine and applied arts departments in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba and other tertiary institutions using construction, welding techniques etc. by Lecturers.*

Keywords: Light Box, Tracing, 3D, Graphics support, Glass surface

Introduction

The relevance of the various branches of visual arts expression in the context of industrial development in contemporary time has increased the desirability of improving the teaching and learning of Fine and Applied Arts in schools and Colleges. Therefore, it has become necessary to write in black and white on the need to revisit the use of light box and bring to the knowledge of the art students the importance of this subject matter and to embrace it altogether. Graphics is one of the branches of visual arts. It is also one of the major areas that has experience dramatic breakthrough in technological invention as it has undergone several developmental stages. Graphics, as a versatile medium of creative expression has continued to evolve overtime. Uzoagba, (2008) emphasized that of all the different branches of arts; graphics art demands the greatest artistic expression and draughtsman ship. In this era where graphic tools and equipment have been taken over by computer, the frequent production of software packages for effective and efficient execution of works of art has continue to usher in novel challenges. The artistic tools and equipment used in graphics offers a wide variety of flexibility for greater creative output.

The availability of computer and software packages has, to a large extent made art students and art professionals to abandon some of the tools and equipment used in graphics. There are different tools and equipment used in graphics for effective and durable designs amongst which is light box.

It is against this backdrop that the researchers deemed it necessary to produced light box for use by art students to enhance their artistic skill and knowledge development. Light box is a translucent surface where a shape laid upon the surface needs to be seen with high contrast. The interesting aspect of light box is the way images are reproduced through the process of drawing, tracing and sketching. However, there are different types of light box commonly used by artists and professionals. These light boxes are of different types and shapes, and they differ in functionality. When light boxes are properly explored, they offer a lot of benefits to include the provision of perfect opportunity to enhance problem-solving skills

Statement of the Problem

Graphics is one of the major branches of visual arts that has experience breakthrough in technological advancement. Graphics art demands the greatest artistic expression and

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draughtsman ship. In this dispensation where graphics tools and equipment have been taken over by the computer, there seems to be gross neglect of some of the tools and equipment used in graphic designs. It is against this backdrop that the researchers deemed it necessary to produce graphics light box for use by art students to enhance their artistic skills. Light box is necessary for total development of students' artistic skills, more importantly in its creative process.

Hypothesis

H¹ There is a significant relationship between the availability and use of light box /table and the creative performance of applied art students graphically

Research questions

1. To what extent is the use of light box significant on the creative performance of applied art students graphically?
2. How can affordable, LARGE and quality Light box/table be made for applied art students' use? This will be answered by outlining the production procedure and process.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to construct a light box for use by art students for effective studio performance.

Specifically, the objectives of this study will be to:

1. Identify the various materials used for the construction of a light box.
2. Find out the attitude of students towards the use of light box
3. Find out whether adequate attention is given to the light box by the students.

Scope of the study:

There are different types of light box used by different people and for different purposes. While some are used by professionals, others are used by artists in art studios and doctors' offices for backlighting X-rays and photographic negatives. However for the purpose of this study, the research will focus on the construction of graphic light box used by art students in graphic studios.

Significance of the Study

The research exposes art students to the techniques of using the light box for effective studio performance. This fosters a practical approach that creates interfaces and generates more interest in the act of using light box. It is also important for the teachers to assist students develop their creativity on the use of the light box. The main concern of this work is to encourage and promote the use of the light box for teaching and learning.

With the light box, students will be exposed to the techniques of creating images. It will also help to build confidence on the students. An important function with the light box is that it can be used for drawing, tracing and sketching.

Visual Art:

Right from the Pre-historic era, arts have always existed. Its functions cut across social, cultural and economic life of the people because art focuses on the development of the totality of man, thereby making him or her useful in the society. According to Ogumor, (2007), art generally is a way of life. He emphasized further that art means any skill, trade, craft or acquired expertise. In the same token, Hornby, (2015) noted that art is the use of the imagination to express ideas or feelings, particularly in painting, drawing or sculpture. Uzoagba, (2008) is of the view that art is a human conception made manifest by the skillful use of a medium. In this context therefore the restrictions of the contemporary concepts of art to skills are used to arouse acceptable aesthetic knowledge inclusive of the other fundamental functionality to include religious and utilitarianism. Avae, (2007) Opines that art is the highest form of human expression and a reflection of the society that creates it. From all indications, it can be observed that art helps to develop our skills and fosters critical appreciation of a work of art and its aesthetic qualities. In this contemporary era of academic consciousness and scientific developments, art should be seen as a social, economic and technological tool for classical socio-cultural engagements and economic freedom.

Concepts of Graphics:

All through history, technological advancement has shaped the development of graphic art. Graphics is one of the branches of visual arts. It is also one of the major areas that has experience dramatic breakthrough in technological invention as it has undergone several developmental

stages. Graphics, as a versatile medium of creative expression has continued to evolve overtime. Uzoagba (2008) emphasized that of all the different branches of arts, graphics art demands the greatest artistic expression and draughtsman ship. In this era where graphic tools and equipment have been taken over by computer, the frequent production of software packages for effective and efficient execution of works of art has continue to usher in novel challenges. The artistic tools and equipment used in graphics offers a wide variety of flexibility for greater creative output.

According to the New Encyclopaedia Britannica, (2007) graphic design is the art and profession of selecting and arranging visual elements such as typography, images, symbols and colors to convey a message to an audience. Graphic design can also be referred to as visual communication. The essential part of graphic design is the task of combining visual and verbal elements into an orderly and effective whole. This is supported by Uzoagba, (2008) when he said that Art is a way to clarify and fix ideas in the minds through visual reiteration by strengthening what has been learnt about something. Right from the medieval period graphic design has been practiced in various forms. This dates back to the manuscripts in ancient Egypt, Greece and China. In 15th century, the development of printing and production of books also led to the advancement in graphic designs. In the late 19th century, during the Industrial Revolution, graphic design emerged as a distinctive vocation in the West as a result of the new technologies and commercial possibilities. Throughout the 20th century, the technology available to designers continued to progress swiftly. As the profession expanded, graphic designers created book jackets, compact-disc covers, trademarks, magazine pages, advertisements, motion pictures, packaging, kinetic titles for television programs, postage stamps and websites. At inception of the 21st century, as technology advances, industries stretch all through the world and graphic design become a global profession.

Light box:

A **light box/table** is a viewing device that is used to review photographic film or artwork placed on top of it. A horizontal form of a self-standing light box, it provides even illumination of the subject from below through a translucent cover and fluorescent lights that emit little heat. They are mainly used in the trades of graphics to trace designs, especially in the world of cartoon or comics. Another use is for example to review film negatives photoliths or any kind of artwork that

can be placed on top of a table for working with it. In general: professional tracing, animation, cartoons, design and drawing creation, education, architecture, interior design, fashion, in hospitals for viewing radiographs

This study will provide the technical and professional knowledge and experience to the students so as to meet the learning requirements needed for using this. Some light tables may be like big light boxes horizontally standing on some type of support (legs) allowing users to lay sheets of paper or films on their work surface to easily view or trace them while being comfortably seated on an office chair, the one for this study would be made up of six viewing glass points or viewing areas that can be used by three pairs or multiple users at the same time rather than that of a single user which is majorly in the market.

Art is seen as a process of acquiring and developing skills with the use of available art materials through experimentation and manipulation. Uzoagba, (2008) is of the view that, in this present dispensation of academic consciousness and technological advancement, art students should strive to become a creative and experimental worker. In this sense, the importance of light box to the overall acquisition of knowledge and practical skills cannot be ignored. There are a number of creative industries using a tool called light box. However, we are specifically referring to a box with a diffused light in it. The box is made up of multiple LED bulbs that illuminate the surface, giving opportunity to the users to see illuminated images more easily.

Types of light box/Light tables

Light tables are built with high-quality materials and are available in different styles with many customizable features. Light tables can be adapted to many different workplaces, including medical, tough laboratory and industrial uses, as well as use by independent artists. There are different types of light box commonly used by artists and professionals. These light boxes are of different shapes and sizes and they differ in functionality. The shape can be square, round or rectangular. They include:

1. Sign-level light box
2. Roof light box
3. Backlit light box
4. Edge lit light box

5. Fabric SEG light box
6. Snap frame light box
7. Gagene table light box
8. Standard and Drafting Light Tables
9. Tilting Light Tables
10. Height Adjustable Light Tables
11. Mobile Light Tables etc.

The methodology

The study is an art-based action research which combined standard qualitative research methodology with the art based technique of production/ creation of the light box. To answer RQ1 [Research Question one] questionnaires were used to obtain data for the inquiry, sought directly from learners and teachers in tertiary art departments while production method detailing step by step process were used to answer RQ2. The method used was measuring, cutting and assemblage of the wood, board and glasses with necessary tools/equipment to achieve the desired output.

Population for the study

All the one hundred (100) respondents from five (5) tertiary institutions from the southern part of Nigeria including staff and students of the Department of Fine and Applied Arts, Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

Table 1: Summary of Art Schools and Number of Respondents

S/N	SCHOOLS	NO: RESPONDENTS	
		LECTURERS	STUDENTS
1	Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	10	10
2	University of Benin, Benin City	10	10
3	University of Nigeria, Nsukka	10	10
4	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka	10	10
5	Auchi Polytechnic, Auchi	10	10
	TOTAL	50	50
	GRAND TOTAL		100

Sampling Technique

A simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting these five schools, Lecturers and Students largely based on distance and proximity to the research area

Demographic analysis

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	60	54.5%
Female	40	45.5%
Total	100	100%

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by Status

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Teachers	9	9.1%
Students	91	90.9%
Total	100	100%

Preliminary sketches and models drawings of the light box

Light Table: lightbox work plan/sketch
Top View

Plate 1:
Name: Outline, Front view of light box/
table
Size: 8 by 4 feet
Height: 3feet

Plate 2:
Name: 3D Outline of light box

Three Dimensional sketch outline

Plate 3:
Name: 3D colored rendering

Coloured three D Output

Materials used for the production of the functional/wooden Graphic light box/table.

Materials

Box- made of Oak wood
Tempered 4mm glasses
H- Tape
MBF board
Hinges
Screws ½, 2inches
Gum
Scissors
Measuring tape
Light fixtures. [6pcs of 5 Watts white bulbs and lamp holders.]
Electrical hardware/Cord (an outlet and switch)
Board

Equipment

Ventilation driller/bits
Driller machine
Glass grinder/cutter
Screw driller
Circular Sew/ Blades
Jig Sew

The other materials that were used in the course of this research include wood, board, tape, handsaw (different types), different sizes of nails, top bond, hammers, glasses, wires, sockets, and bulbs.

Instrument for Data Collection

A 6 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. The instrument used was titled: **Graphics Light box Revisited Questionnaire (GLBRQ)**. The use of questionnaire made the process empirical, easier and more accurate. The questionnaire was designed with a four (4) point rating scale which was made up of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instrument was divided into two sections A and B. Section ‘A’ was to cover the area of demographic details of respondents while ‘B’ focused on the subject matter of the study.

Data analysis and interpretation of results

This aspect focused on data analysis and interpretation of results generated with research question one. Descriptive statistics was used covering frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation. SPSS was used as the tool for data analysis

Research question one

To what extent is the use of light box significant on the creative performance of applied art students graphically?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

s/n		N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
	Q4	100	1.0	4.0	3.470	.8343
	Q1	100	1.0	4.0	2.800	1.1721
	Q2	100	1.0	4.0	3.310	1.0120
	Q3	100	1.0	4.0	3.620	.8013
	Q5	100	1.0	4.0	2.150	.7300
	Q6	100	1.0	4.0	3.850	.5925
	Valid N (listwise)	100				

Table 5: Response to questions on the use/value and significance of Light box to applied art students

S/N	ITEMS	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	MEAN	STD	DECISION	EXT.
	The use and value of graphic lightbox/table								
1	It provides comfort and serves s work station convenient for skillful graphic reproductions	40	20	20	20	2.8	1.17	Agree	HE
2	Light box is essential to the technique of tracing for young artist and designers	61	19	10	10	3.3	1.01	Agree	VHE
3	The lighting supplied by light box/table helps correct students visual inefficiency due to insufficient studio lights	77	13	5	5	3.6	0.80	Agree	VHE
4	It helps develop the skill of graphical outlining and drawing manually	63	27	4	6	3.5	0.83	Agree	VHE
5	light box is not an improved technical support for applied arts students	10	5	75	10	2.2	0.73	Disagree	LE
6	light box provides additional motivation for stress less task for graphic students	93	2	2	3	3.9	0.59	Agree	VHE
	GRAND MEAN					3.2		Agree	VHE

The table above shows that there is a positive acceptance and agreement from the respondents regarding the value/ use, need and significance of the light table to applied arts students. Most of the means are above 2.5 to high and very high extent except for item 5 which respondents disagreed with. This further buttresses the fact that the light table is not only useful if available but also very needful as a technical tool/equipment for graphic tasks to very high extent.

The Grand mean of 3.2 also attest to the submission and hypothesis that; there is a significant relationship between the availability and use of light box / table and the creative performance of applied art students graphically.

Research question two

How can affordable, large and quality Light box/table be made for applied art students' use?

This will be answered by outlining the production procedure and steps

Processes/procedures of production are as follows:

Step 1: Build a Rectangular Box to House the Lights/Glass Top

- a. Measurements of all parts, height, width and length
- b. Cutting
- c. Joining with screws/hinges
- d. Fixing of H-tapes on all edges

Step 2: Create Ventilation Holes to Provide Air Circulation.

- a. also serves as assess point for picture placement

Step 3: Install the Electrical Components

Step 4: install glass hardwares

Step 5: final finishing and clean up

- a. Final assemblage

Plate 4: Full MBF Boards to be used as best alternative for

Plate 5: Activities of measuring and cutting table dimension

Aok Wood.

Plate 6: Measuring and cutting of the stand for both sides of
The table.

Plate 7: Researcher Measuring the length of the table

Plate 9: Researcher screwing the table stand

Plate 8: Cutting and assemblage of glass frame for the table

Plate 10: Assembled glass frame

Plate 11: Researcher and research assistant sharing ideas
together

Plate 12: H- Tapes used on the edges of cut boards and glass frame

Plate 13: Application of H Tape on the glass frame

Plate 14: Finished glass frame with six spaces, three on each side

Plate 15: Researcher screwing the table stand

Plate 16: Researchers checking the balance of both table Stand

Plate 17: Access points cover with ventilation and hinges holes

Plate 18: Two sides of the box stand with six access points into the box

Plate 19: Application of gum and H-Tape to the access point cover

Plate 20: Finished table stands ready for assemblage

Plate 21: Finished glass frame ready for assemblage

Plate 22: Assembled table with open access point without glass frame

Plate 23: Left side of assembled table without glass frame

Plate 24: Six glass slides ready for installation on table frame

Plate 25: Finished table with installed glass top

Plate 26: Finished light box / table with all the electrical components and glass hard wares

Plate 27: Researchers with finished table

Plate 28: Finished table

Plate 29: Equipment used during the research

Plate 30 Table top with wired bulb lights

Plate 31: DrillerScrewer

Plate 32: Researchers during a workshop session

Summary of the findings

The following are the summary of our findings throughout the research exercise:

The absence of a functional Light box has hindered students from acquiring necessary creative and technical skills

The production of the light box /table will go a long way to improve students' interest, increase students graphic skills particularly with image tracing and design reproduction.

To a very large extent, the availability of a new light box will enhance the quality of lessons received by students from the lecturers

The findings revealed that only few art departments in other schools visited possess a functional light box/ light table for studio performance. This suggests the need for holistic studio equipment upgrade nationwide.

The findings also revealed that developed preliminary sketches and measurements required little adjustments, especially with height to match the latest standard dimension in use.

It was equally discovered that this study will save students time and money as they engage in their practical courses in both graphics and textile courses in Fine and Applied Arts Department.

Discussion

The study is a production of a 3D light box/table meant to support the effort of students and solve the challenges of embarking on visual tracing, image productions without a light box technology. The purpose of the study was to construct a light box for use by art students for effective studio performance. Specifically, the objectives of this study was to: Identify the various materials used for the construction of a light box, find out the attitude of students towards the use of light box whether adequate attention is given to the light box by the students.

The data obtain from six item questionnaire used to answer research question one have been clearly presented on table 3 and 4. Stating unequivocally the need for functional light box in improvised students studio performance to a very high extent. While a step by step production technique was employed in the production of an 8 x 4 feet 3Dimensional light box using above listed materials/equipment. The researchers utilized both descriptive statistics and art/practice based action research methodology to make the study an empirical, qualitative and practical exercise for richer presentation. The researchers were able to seek the opinions and response from both lectures and students from four other Departments of Fine and Applied Arts in four other tertiary institutions close by.

Wooden board, screws, 4mm glass, were the main materials used in the practical production of the light box along with simple equipment e.g. drillers, jig sew, industrial sew etc.

These materials were considered the best for the researchers' desired outputs; they were sought at various points, purchased and utilized in the now ready product of a light table.

Conclusion

The study was carried out from preliminary studies, sketches and finally researched. There is very present need for supplies of practical equipment and teaching aids for practice based courses/ programmes in tertiary institutions. The light box is one addition that would change the narrative of applied arts students in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made:

- There should be an increased practical research to produce additional needed equipment for Fine and Applied Arts Departments in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba and other tertiary institutions using construction, welding techniques etc. by Lecturers.
- More artistic activities utilizing the skill and knowledge of all staff and students of various art departments should be encourage solving certain pressing challenges with locally sourced solutions with the schools.
- More Tetfund research grants should be made available to sponsor similar projects within tertiary institution

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